

КОММУНИКАТИВНО-РЕЧЕВОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА С ЗАДЕРЖКОЙ РЕЧЕВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ

COMMUNICATIVE-SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF YOUNG CHILDREN WITH SPEECH DELAY

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В статье обсуждается важность коммуникативного и речевого развития в жизни детей раннего возраста с задержкой речевого развития. Рассмотрены понятия задержки речевого развития и коммуникативно-речевого развития детей раннего возраста. Выявлены особенности коммуникативно-речевого развития детей раннего возраста с задержкой речевого развития. Описаны коэффициенты компонентов коммуникативно-речевого развития детей раннего возраста с задержкой речевого развития. В исследовании приняли участие 12 детей с задержкой речевого развития. Анализ показал, что маленькие дети с задержкой речевого развития имеют отрицательное значение по сравнению с детьми с нормой, которые имеют положительные значения по выбранным компонентам. Результаты исследования подтверждают важность коммуникативного и речевого развития детей раннего возраста с задержкой речевого развития.

The article discusses the importance of communicative and speech development in the lives of young children with delayed speech development. The concepts of delayed speech development and communicative speech development of young children are considered. The features of the communicative and speech development of young children with delayed speech development are revealed. The coefficients of the components of the communicative and speech development of young children with delayed speech development are described. The study involved 12 young children with delayed speech development. The analysis showed that young children with delayed speech development have a negative value compared to children with the norm, who have positive values for the selected components. The results of the study confirm the importance of the communicative and speech development of young children with delayed speech development.

Ключевые слова: *задержка речевого развития, ранний возраст, коммуникативно-речевое развитие, дети, развитие.*

Key words: *delayed speech development, early age, communicative and speech development, children, development.*

Introduction.

Recently, the number of newborn children with any health problems has been increasing, which in some cases leads to a decrease in the level of speech development.

At an early age, mastering speech as a means of communication is the main line of development of the child, functioning in inextricable connection with the development of the sensory, sensorimotor, intellectual, affective-volitional spheres of the child (L.S. Vygotsky, N.I. Zhinkin, etc.) [2; 5]. Issues of diagnosis and prevention of speech disorders do not lose their relevance due to the constant increase in the number of children with primary and secondary speech pathology and de-

termine the need to provide speech therapy assistance to children as early as possible (O.A. Gorlova, O.E. Gromova, O.G. Prikhodko, E.V. Sheremetyeva, etc.) [3; 4; 7; 9]. In the second or third year of life, the child's active assimilation of speech means of communication begins, and speech problems at this age are defined as "delayed speech development" (SDD) of both a rapid and persistent nature in children in whom deviations from normal speech ontogenesis are quite pronounced, however, the type of speech disorder has not yet been determined [8].

According to O.A. Gorlova: "The communicative and speech development of young children is a process of development of speech activity, during which the child interacts with adults (peers), using means and ways of expressing thoughts and relationships that are adequate to the communicative situation" [3].

Young children with a complicated medical history need early correctional and developmental support and are the focus of attention of speech pathologists, educational psychologists, and speech therapists. The practical significance of studying early child development is confirmed those What in a timely manner carried out diagnostics and correctional work gives opportunity to correct arisen delays V development speech and communicative activities and prevent emergence secondary deviations V development child.

Such famous teachers and defectologists as O.E. dealt with the problems of studying speech development delays. O.E. Gromova, O.G. Prikhodko, E.V. Sheremetyeva et al. [4; 7; 9].

In cases of mental retardation, there is variability in the causes of speech underdevelopment. The rate of development of a child's speech with delayed speech development is characterized by slowness and lag from the norm, while the patterns of formation of lexical and grammatical structures in impressive and expressive speech correspond to normal ontogenesis. In case of mental retardation, the child's communication is limited, communicative activity decreases, interpersonal interaction is insufficient, the emotional sphere suffers, the amount of information received decreases, which impedes the harmonious formation of the child's psyche.

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Purpose of the study: to identify the communicative and speech characteristics of young children with developmental disabilities.

Research methodology and organization.

The following methods were used during the study:

- Theoretical: analysis of psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature on the research problem;
- Empirical: analysis of the products of children's speech activity, method of qualitative and quantitative analysis of research results.

The study involved 12 young children with mental retardation, including 9 boys and 3 girls. Average age – 2 years 8 months. and 3 years attending OSAOU OK "Algorithm of Success" in the Belgorod region.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study was made up of the works dedicated to revealing the characteristics of the communicative development of children (G.M. Andreeva, L.S. Vygotsky, M.I. Lisina, etc.) [1; 2; 5], scientific and methodological works devoted to the problem of developmental development in young children, such scientists like O.A. Gorlova, O.E. Gromova, A.G. Prikhodko and others. [3; 4; 7], works of such researchers as G.V. Chirkina, E.V. Shere-

meteyeva et al. [8; 9], who note the features of communicative and speech development in young children with developmental disabilities.

The study was carried out according to a single plan for everyone children, experimental material and sequence presentation the assignments did not change. The examination procedure involved the use of adequate tasks appropriate to the age of the children.

When assessing each of the criteria according to the methodology of E.V. Sheremeteva [9] determined its coefficient using the formula $X = \frac{\sum x}{n}$: n , where X is the corresponding coefficient; $\sum$ – summation sign, $x (n)$ – points scored by all children of the subgroup, n – number of children.

After the diagnosis was carried out qualitative analysis received data and their quantitative processing, after which the research results were summarized and on their basis were formulated conclusions about the level development everyone child.

Research results and their rationale.

When analyzing the family history, we studied the nature of the somatic pathology of the parents (see Table 1).

Table 1. Results of studying anamnestic data

Sign	mothers' data	fathers data
Diseases of the circulatory system	4	5
Endocrine diseases	2	0
Central nervous system diseases	2	2
Gastrointestinal diseases	3	2
Diseases of the spine and musculoskeletal system	0	0

It was found that among mothers who gave birth to children with RRD, the most common pathologies were diseases of the circulatory system, which amounted to 33.3%, and diseases of the digestive system (gastritis, ulcers, cholecystitis, pancreatitis), which amounted to 25%.

Other common pathologies were endocrine diseases and central nervous system diseases (16.7%, respectively). No diseases of the spine or musculoskeletal system were identified in the mothers. One mother had no chronic somatic diseases.

The structure of the father's somatic problems was dominated by diseases of the nervous system (22.2%), pathology of the gastrointestinal tract (22.2%) and circulatory system (55.6%). No diseases of the spine or musculoskeletal system were identified in the fathers.

An analysis of the course of pregnancy in mothers of young children with RRD revealed the following features: threat of miscarriage (16.7%), toxicosis throughout the entire period of gestation (33.3%), moderate and severe anemia (41.7%), stay under stress (8.3%),

Birth pathology was observed in 41.7% of children, mainly asphyxia of the baby, umbilical cord entanglement, prolonged or rapid labor, breech presentation, surgical resolution of labor, anesthesia during childbirth. 60% children have a difficult postnatal period, mainly with frequent acute respiratory viral infections and acute respiratory infections, as well as violations brain blood circulation, diffuse muscle hypotension.

Analysis anamnestic data at stage 1 of diagnostics showed What All children have complicated neurological history. After analyzing the medical records of young children with mental retardation, it was revealed that the early speech development of children is characterized by a lag. U half children babble appeared V 4-5 months (50%), at 25% or 3 children - V 6 months, at the rest 25% or 3 children development babble detained (appearance V 7-10 months). Appearance first words V 1-1.5 of the year (norm) noted in 41.7% of children (5 people), at 1.6-2.0 years - in 33.3% or 4 children. In 25% of subjects (This 3 children) first words appeared Later 2 years.

The results of the study of prenatal, natal and postnatal pathology in young children with RRD are characterized by negative characteristics of indicators (-28). The N coefficient of the study group of children with mental retardation was -2.3. After analyzing the results of the study, we found that 50% had a negative health indicator, the N coefficient corresponded to -3 points. The results of the study of chronic somatic diseases in young children with developmental disorders are characterized by negative indicator characteristics (-5). The S coefficient of the studied group of children with developmental disabilities was -0.42. (see Pic. 1)

Pic. 1. Results of assessing the coefficients of prenatal, natal and postnatal pathology and chronic somatic diseases young children with mental retardation

During the 2nd stage (social-pedagogical) study, the following results were obtained: play activities in young children with developmental disabilities are characterized by negative indicator characteristics (-6). The P coefficient for the study group of children with developmental disabilities was -0.5.

Having analyzed the results of the study, we found that in 25% the development of play actions was lower than in the majority of children in the group, the P coefficient corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -2 points.

The results of a study of speech activity in play in young children with developmental disabilities are characterized by negative indicator characteristics (-2). Ps factor of the studied group of children with developmental disabilities was -0.16.

For the majority of children, more than 58.3%, speech activity in the game was insufficient or absent, the Ps coefficient corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -2 points.

The results of the study on stimulating the need to communicate with a close adult are characterized by a zero-indicator value (0).

In 16.7% of young children there was no need to communicate with a close adult, the M coefficient corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -7 points.

The results of a study of emotional response in play in young children with developmental disabilities are characterized by a negative indicator value (-2). The E coefficient of the studied group of children with mental retardation was -0.16 points.

In 25% of children, the emotional response in the game was reduced; coefficient E corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -2 points. Also, for 25%, the emotional response in the

game was insufficient or absent, the E coefficient corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -2 points.

The results of the speech therapy diagnostic stage (3 stages) included assessment parameters and the results of studying the state of the components of the intonation system in young children with developmental disabilities. The study revealed that the tone of voice in young children with developmental disabilities is characterized by a negative indicator value (-2). The TV coefficient of the studied group of children with mental retardation was -0.16 points.

The results of the study of melody in young children with developmental disabilities are characterized by a negative indicator value (-3). The MV coefficient of the studied group of children with mental retardation was -0.25 points.

The results of the study of rhythm in young children with mental retardation are characterized by a negative value of indicators (-5). The MV coefficient of the studied group of children with mental retardation was -0.41 points.

In the majority of children, more than 58.3%, the basic tone of the voice does not correspond to the intonation-rhythmic characteristics of normal speech development; the TV coefficient corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -1 point.

In 50% of children with developmental disabilities, the melody of the voice does not correspond to the intonation-rhythmic characteristics of normal speech development; the MV coefficient corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -1 point.

In the majority of children (58.3%), the rhythm of the voice does not correspond to the intonation and rhythmic characteristics of normal speech development, coefficient Rh corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -1 point.

Thus, in the majority of young children with mental retardation, intonation and rhythmic indicators, such as tone of voice, melody, and rhythm, are reduced.

The results of the study of motor prerequisites in young children with developmental disabilities are characterized by a negative indicator value (-4). The LA coefficient of the labial muscles of the studied group of children with developmental disorders was 0.33 points. When assessing the results of studying motor prerequisites in young children with developmental disorders, it was revealed that in children, the range of movements of the labial muscles is sufficient, the lips take part in the capture of liquid and solid food bolus, the manifestation of the nasolabial fold is one-sided. In 33.3% of children, the labial muscles were underdeveloped, the LA coefficient corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -3 points.

The TA coefficient of the tongue muscles of the studied group of children with mental retardation was -0.75 points.

In the majority of children with mental retardation (66.7%), the tongue muscles are underdeveloped, the TA coefficient corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -2 points. The JA coefficient of the mandibular muscles in the studied group of children with developmental disorders was -0.83. All children with early developmental developmental disorders get tired quickly when chewing solid food. In 50% of children with mental retardation, the mandibular muscles are underdeveloped; the JA coefficient corresponded to a negative value and amounted to -2 points. Thus, in the majority of young children with mental retardation, motor prerequisites are not sufficiently developed.

The results of a study of phonemic perception in young children with developmental disabilities are characterized by a negative indicator value (-36). The Ph coefficient for differentiation of sounds in the studied group of children with developmental disabilities was -3 points. When assessing the results of studying phonemic perception in young children with developmental disabilities, it was found that 100% of preschoolers do not differentiate sounds (hard-soft, hissing, whistling sounds), only 50% of children with developmental disabilities differentiated the vowels o-u.

The coefficients for studying the components of communicative and speech development of

young children with developmental disabilities are presented in Pic. 2.

Pic. 2. Results of assessing the coefficients of components of communicative and speech development of young children with developmental disabilities

The discussion of the results.

All coefficients of the components of communicative and speech development of young children with developmental disabilities have a negative value, which coincides with the data of E.V. Sheremeteva (58), the author points out that in young children with developmental disabilities, the coefficients of the components of communicative and speech development have a negative value in comparison with children with the norm, who have positive values for the selected components. In the presented sample of children, the most pronounced negative value is made up of the coefficients: Ph (-3) insufficient development of phonemic perception, insufficient development of motor prerequisites, namely the mandibular muscles JA (-1.3) and the tongue muscles TA (-0.75).

After conducting the study, we received the following results. Early speech development of children is characterized by a lag. In 50%, babbling appeared at 4-5 months, in 25% - at 6 months, in the remaining 25%, the appearance of babbling was delayed (at 7-10 months). The normal appearance of the first words at 1-1.5 years was observed in 41.7% of children, at 1.6-2.0 years - in 33.3%. In 25% of subjects, their first words appeared after 2.5 years.

We studied medical documentation and developmental histories of children. Analysis of the course of pregnancy revealed the following features: threat of miscarriage (16.7%), toxicosis (33.3%), anemia (41.7%), stress (8.3%). Disturbances during childbirth were observed in 41.7% of children; asphyxia, umbilical cord entanglement, prolonged or rapid labor, incorrect positioning, surgery, and anesthesia during childbirth were identified. 60% of children have a difficult postnatal period, mainly with frequent acute respiratory viral infections and acute respiratory infections.

Conclusions.

Thus, as a result of our research, it was found that children have a low level of development of communicative and speech activity, which is expressed in insufficient development of phonemic perception, insufficient development of motor prerequisites, namely the mandibular muscles and muscles of the tongue.

This study confirms the importance of communicative and speech development throughout the entire correctional and educational process of young children with developmental disabilities and indicates the need for targeted correctional work.

Analysis of theoretical sources made it possible to determine that timely diagnosis and correctional work makes it possible to correct any delays in the development of speech and communication activities and prevent the occurrence of secondary deviations in the development of the child.

Features of the communicative and speech development of young children with developmental disabilities are the following: burdened neurological history, insufficient speech activity in play, lack of need to communicate with a close adult, low emotional response in play, reduced intonation and rhythmic indicators such as tone of voice, melody, rhythm.

This is due to the need to study the communicative and speech development of young children with developmental disabilities.

A low level of communicative and speech development has a negative impact on the formation of all communicative and speech activities as a whole and prevents full learning. This issue requires the intervention of various specialists in the field of correction of speech disorders and shows the importance of communicative speech development of speech in young children suffering from speech development disorders.

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